

Effect of some Factors on the Stability of Yttrium Complexes with Salicylamide and Salicylanilide

(Miss) SAVINDRA GREWAL, B. S. SEKHON, B. S. PANNU and S. L. CHOPRA*

Department of Chemistry & Biochemistry, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana.

Manuscript received 16 October 1974 ; revised 24 February 1975 ; accepted 17 March 1975

The effect of ionic strength and dielectric constant of the medium on the pK and stability constant of the yttrium complexes with salicylamide & salicylanilide in water-dioxan medium at 25° has been studied. The stability and protonation constants of the ligands increase with the increasing composition of dioxan whereas the stability varies inversely with the increasing ionic strength of the medium. The stabilities of the salicylamide complexes were found to be higher as compared to salicylanilide complexes.

AMONGST the trivalent ions, yttrium by virtue of its resemblance to rare earth metal ions, is expected to form strong complexes. Not enough data are available on the complexes of yttrium with phenolic ligands such as salicylamide and related compounds. In the present study, the stability constants of yttrium complexes with salicylamide and salicylanilide have been determined in 50% (v/v) dioxan-water medium at 25° so as to study the effect of ionic strength. The effect of varying the composition of the medium on the pK values of the ligands and the stability constants of yttrium complexes has been studied at ionic strength of 0.1M and 25°.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade. Salicylamide and salicylanilide were prepared and purified by the known methods^{1,2}. Carbonate free sodium hydroxide was prepared by the standard method³. Dioxan was purified by the method of Riddick and Toops⁴.

A stock solution of $Y(NO_3)_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ (E. Merck) was prepared in calculated quantity of perchloric acid to prevent hydrolysis. The metal content was estimated by precipitating its oxalate and then dissolved it in sulphuric acid and titrating the liberated oxalic acid against standard permanganate solution. The solutions of the ligands were prepared in dioxan and were standardized potentiometrically.

The pH titrations were carried out in a glass cell with a jacket for circulating water from a thermostat maintained at 25°. 'Systronix' pH meter standardized with buffers of pH 4.00 and 9.10 was used. The pH readings were accurate within ± 0.02 .

For each set of experiments, three titrations were carried out adopting Irving-Rossotti method⁵. Since pH titration studies were carried out in dioxan water medium, appropriate correction as per Van Uitert and Haas⁶ was applied for measurements. Solutions containing (1) free mineral acid (0.05M); (2) free mineral acid + ligand (0.05M) and (3) free mineral acid + ligand +

metal ion (0.01M) were titrated with a standard solution of sodium hydroxide. The initial volume of solution was 20 ml and the desired ionic strengths were maintained by the addition of sodium perchlorate solution.

Results and Discussion

The results obtained from the titration of various ligands in the absence and presence of metal ions were plotted and the values of proton stability constants, calculated from these curves according to Irving and Rossotti⁵ are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1 - PROTONATION CONSTANTS OF SALICYLAMIDE AND SALICYLANILIDE AT 25°

Volume% dioxan	Ionic strength	Log K_1^H		
		Salicylamide	Salicylanilide	
25	0.10	9.15	8.40	
	50	0.05	10.11	8.85
		0.10	10.00	8.81
		0.20	9.85	8.77
		0.30	9.60	8.75
70	0.10	10.61	9.05	

The values of \bar{n} and pL obtained from titration data using the method of Irving and Rossotti, were employed to draw the formation curves representing \bar{n} as a function of pL of yttrium complexes with ligands (Figs. 1,2). The values of stability constants were obtained by various computational methods⁷ and are reported in Tables 2 and 3. The values of stability constants are accurate to ± 0.05 log units.

TABLE 2 - STABILITY CONSTANTS OF YTTRIUM-SALICYLAMIDE COMPLEXES IN DIOXANE-WATER MIXTURE AT 25°.

Volume % dioxan	Ionic Strength	Log K_1	Log K_2	Log K_3	Log β_3	
25	0.10	4.85	4.20	3.50	12.55	
	50	0.05	6.40	5.70	4.40	16.50
		0.10	6.20	5.42	4.35	15.97
		0.20	5.96	5.22	4.05	15.23
		0.30	5.70	5.08	3.80	14.58
		0.00	6.75	6.00	4.80	17.55
70	0.10	8.75	6.82	6.30	21.87	

* For Correspondence

Fig. 1 Formation Curves for Yttrium Complexes in 50:50 Dioxan : Water Mixture at 25° : (A) Salicylamide, (B) Salicylanilide

Fig. 2 Metal-Ligand Formation Curves at 25° and $\mu = 0.1M$ In Dioxan Water Mixtures (A) 70:30 (B) 50:50 (C) 25:75 (a—Salicylamide, b—Salicylanilide.)

TABLE 3—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF YTTRIUM-SALICYLANILIDE COMPLEXES IN DIOXANE-WATER MIXTURE AT 25°.

Volume % dioxan	Ionic Strength	Log K ₁	Log K ₂	Log K ₃	Log β ₃
25	0.10	4.20	3.80	2.58	10.58
50	0.05	4.92	4.45	3.92	13.29
	0.10	4.75	4.30	3.85	12.90
	0.20	4.65	4.20	3.80	12.65
	0.30	4.50	4.13	3.75	12.38
	0.00	5.20	4.65	4.02	13.87
70	0.10	5.25	4.80	4.52	14.57

The titration studies indicate that yttrium complexes of both the ligands have 1:3 stoichiometry. The differences in the values of log K₁ and log K₂ and also in the values of log K₂ and log K₃ for yttrium complexes in each case are less than 1.5, thus suggesting that formation of three types of complexes, ML, ML₂ and ML₃ proceed simultaneously and the metal-ligand equilibria can be expressed as :

If the ligands are represented by structural formula I, the pK of the ligands, (Table 1), increase for substituent, R, as follows :

The stability of the complexes formed by the metal also increases in the same order showing that the donation of the electrons is determined by the basicity of the ligands. The values of log β_n of salicylamide complexes are higher in comparison to salicylanilide complexes. Similar findings for the variation of the log K₁ values with pK of some hydroxy ligands have also been shown by Charan Das and Rao⁸ in their studies on beryllium complexes.

Effect of Ionic Strength : The stability data for log β_n values suggest that with an increase in the ionic strength of the medium, the values of stability constants of salicylamide and salicylanilide decrease. According to Huckel⁹, the relation between activity coefficient of an ion and the ionic strength for concentrations of 0.01M and higher is given below :

$$-\ln \gamma_i = \frac{Z_i^2 \alpha \mu^{\frac{1}{2}}}{1 + \beta a_i \mu^{\frac{1}{2}}} - b_i \mu$$

showing that the activity of the metal ion for its interaction with other molecular species decreases with the increase in the ionic strength of the medium in which the reactions are studied. Thus the increasing ionic strength of the medium decreases the formation vis a vis the stabilities of Y(III) complexes for both salicylamide and salicylanilide and this is also in agreement with the findings of Debye¹⁰.

Thermodynamic Stability Constants : The thermodynamic stability constants were obtained by extrapolation of the plots (Fig. 3) of log β_n Vs μ^{1/2} to zero ionic strength and the values of log K₁, log K₂, log K₃ and log β₃ at zero ionic strength are also reported in Tables 2 and 3 for salicylamide and salicylanilide

complexes respectively. The value of log β₃ is 17.55 for salicylamide complexes whereas the corresponding value of log β₃ for salicylanilide complexes is 13.87 thus showing that salicylamide complexes are of greater stability than salicylanilide complexes. This is due to the fact that pK values of salicylamide are higher than pK values of salicylanilide in all cases. Since in complex formation, the donation of the electrons is determined by the basicity of the ligands, and this justifies the greater stability of salicylamide complexes.

Fig. 3 Plot of log β₃ vs √μ for yttrium complexes (1) salicylamide (2) salicylanilide.

Effect of Dielectric Constant : According to Van Uitert *et al*¹¹ there is a linear relationship between the stability constants of certain acetylacetonate complexes and the mole fraction of dioxane used in the solvent to change the dielectric constant of the medium. It appears that this relationship is generally valid for oxygen donor ligands¹². The variation of log K₁, log K₂, log K₃ and log β_n with n_x of dioxan in the medium can be represented by :

$$\log K = a n_x + b$$

The results reported in Tables 2 and 3 show that decrease in dielectric constant with n_x of the dioxan favours greater association of ions resulting in higher log K values. This means that the product formed during the reaction is less polar in medium of lower dielectric constant as compared to product formed in a medium of higher dielectric constant. It is also observed that there is a regular decrease in stabilities in dioxane solution in passing from ML→ML₂→ML₃. Since salicylamide and salicylanilide are also oxygen donor ligands and thus the above linear relationship between the stability constants of salicylamide and salicylanilide complexes and mole fraction of dioxane used in the solvent to change the dielectric constant of medium, is valid.

From the relationship log K = a n_x + b, the values of slopes (a) and intercepts (b) were obtained. The values of (a) for log K₁, log K₂, log K₃, log β₃ are 15.0, 11.3, 11.7 and 36.0 in case of salicylamide complexes and 4.2, 3.8, 7.0 and 15.0 in case of salicylanilide complexes.

Thus it is inferred that the slopes are higher for salicylamide than salicylanilide which accounts for their greater stabilities. The intercepts for $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$, $\log K_3$ and $\log \beta_3$ are 4.0, 3.7, 2.7 and 10.6 for salicylamide and 4.0, 3.6, 2.5 and 10.2 for salicylanilide from which it is inferred that intercepts are almost equal in both cases which accounts for equal stabilities on extrapolations. The eliminations of co-ordinated water molecules¹¹ is also of importance as a cause contributing to medium effect. Thus a reaction of complex formation :

The increase in apparent stability of ML in an aqueous dioxan mixture compared to that in water alone derives in some part from the lower activity of water in dioxan-water compared to these values in pure water. A complete equilibrium constant K^x will, therefore, include a term in the concentration of water and will relate to the apparent formation constant K^x as $K^x = K^x (H_2O)_s^n$, where $(H_2O)_s$ is the concentration of water in mixed solvents. The explanation incorporates the assumption that solvation of reacting species is almost exclusively by water molecules. Since dioxan is also a polar solvent, some of the molecules eliminated may be of dioxan instead of water molecules¹³.

References

1. P. RAMBACHER and J. MIKSCHE, US Pat., 1953, 2, 636, 900; (*Chem. Abs.*, 1954, 48, 4588 h).
2. C. WAGNER D. SINGER and W. WOUFFEN, *Pharmazie*, 1966, 21, 161.
3. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longman's, 1961.
4. J. A. RIDDICK and E. E. TOOPS, "Organic Solvents," Second Edition, Interscience, 1955.
5. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
6. L. G. VAN UITERT and C. G. HAAS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 451.
7. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397.
8. P. CHARAN DAS and G. S. RAO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 49, 547.
9. E. HUCKEL, *Physik. Z.*, 1925, 26, 93.
10. P. DEBYE, *Trans. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1942, 82, 7.
11. L. G. VAN UITERT, C. G. HAAS, W. C. FERNBLIUS and B. E. DOUGHAS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 455.
12. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1956, 10, 72.
13. K. K. MUI and W. A. E. MCBRYDE, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1974, 52, 1821.